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Comparative Analysis of Low-Code/No-code Development
Platforms for the Development of Health Applications by
Non-Technical Medical Professionals.

by

Chukwuebuka Obiora
S5712784

Faculty of Science & Technology
Department of Computing and Informatics
Individual Masters Project

Abstract

Digital health solutions are increasingly required to address health conditions, yet there is a lack the technical expertise to develop necessary applications that must still meet demanding data-protection requirements. Low-Code/No-Code (LCNC) platforms present a potential solution, enabling non-technical medical professionals who have niche knowledge to design and deploy digital tools. However, given the sensitivity of health data, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) remains a significant challenge.

This dissertation evaluates the capacity of two prominent LCNC platforms, Mendix and OutSystems, to support GDPR-compliant health application development. A prototype application for chronic disease management was implemented across both platforms and assessed against five GDPR Articles central to health contexts: Article 5 (data minimisation), Article 6 (lawful processing), Article 7 (consent), Article 25 (privacy by design and default), and Article 32 (security of processing).

The findings reveal that while both platforms provide strong baseline features such as secure authentication, role-based access, and default encryption, they diverge in ease of implementation and configuration demands.

This study contributes a decision-support framework and prescriptive recommendations to guide non-technical medical professionals in selecting LCNC platforms for compliant application development. The results emphasise that LCNC tools can enable app creation, but GDPR compliance is not fully automated.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Problem Context

The healthcare industry is undergoing a rapid and significant digital transformation, driven by the development of eHealth technologies (Bente et al. 2024), a deepened exploration of technological possibilities, and a growing focus on optimising healthcare goals (Van Gemert-Pijnen 2022). This transformation has resulted in increased automation of healthcare processes, birthing numerous benefits, including enhanced interoperability (Zapata et al. 2015), improved data reusability (Ribeiro et al. 2018), streamlined workflows (Patterson et al. 2015), better decision-making support (Berrouguet et al. 2018), and more personalised care (Chute and French 2019).

However, despite these technological advances the development of these tools still largely falls on overburdened IT teams, resulting in slow deployment cycles and limited responsiveness to frontline clinical needs. Furthermore, the implementation of digital health environments continues to face substantial challenges, ranging from ethical and legal concerns to high costs and technical complexity. Ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) or its national counterparts like the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), requires meticulous attention to data security, consent processes, and the safeguarding of sensitive patient information (Kuner et al. 2021; Cummins & Schuller, 2020). These requirements, combined with high development and maintenance costs, place considerable strain on healthcare organisations attempting to adopt digital solutions (Bente et al., 2024).

Additionally, traditional development strategies often face clinician resistance due to poor usability, workflow misalignment, and limited involvement of frontline medical professionals in the design process (Onyeabor et al. 2025). Lloyd et al. (2023) further highlight a growing misalignment: while healthcare providers require adaptive, clinically aligned digital tools, these solutions are often slow to emerge, costly, and unsatisfactory from the end-user's perspective.

1.2 Problem Definition

Empowering medical professionals to develop and deploy digital health solutions tailored to their specific clinical needs has the potential to address many of the current limitations in healthcare's digital transformation. The ability to customise tools for unique workflows and patient populations could lead to faster, more efficient adoption of technology, allowing for improved patient care and streamlined processes. However, this empowerment remains hindered by significant barriers, including the lack of intuitive, user-friendly development platforms that can be utilized by those without deep technical expertise.

Low-Code/No-Code (LCNC) platforms present a promising opportunity to bridge this gap, enabling non-technical users such as medical professionals with minimal coding expertise to rapidly create

digital solutions (Sanchis et al. 2019; Luo et al. 2021). Despite the potential benefits of LCNC platforms in the healthcare sector, there is a paucity of research on their adoption and influence on the healthcare sector. There are concerns about their ease of implementation and compliance with specific GDPR provisions. Furthermore, the usability of these platforms in implementing compliance mechanisms without extensive technical knowledge remains under-researched. There is a need for research to assess how best LCNC platforms can support healthcare needs, whether LCNC platforms can provide intuitive tools and features for non-technical medical professionals to create health applications, and simplify the implementation of compliance measures. Understanding these is crucial in determining their overall efficacy in healthcare settings.

This gap in both research and practical application underscores a critical need to investigate how LCNC platforms can empower medical professionals to develop secure, effective, and compliant healthcare applications. By addressing this issue, we can unlock a pathway for more adaptive, responsive, and cost-effective digital health solutions that align closely with the needs of both clinicians and patients.

1.3 Project Justification

The growing demand for digital transformation in healthcare presents both significant opportunities and challenges. While existing technologies have demonstrated the potential to improve patient care, enhance operational efficiency, and promote personalised treatment plans, their successful implementation and adoption have been hindered by a variety of barriers, including slow deployment cycles, user resistance, and complex regulatory requirements.

By empowering medical professionals with the tools to create their own digital health solutions, this project addresses a critical gap in both healthcare practice and research. The use of LCNC platforms in healthcare holds the potential to revolutionize how digital health solutions are developed and deployed. If medical professionals are empowered to create customised tools that align with their workflows and patient needs, the entire cycle of healthcare technology deployment can be accelerated. This would not only improve the speed at which healthcare services are enhanced but also ensure that the solutions are more directly responsive to the challenges faced by medical professionals.

Moreover, usable LCNC platforms that can support regulatory compliance (GDPR and HIPAA), will contribute to a more sustainable model for digital health applications. It could significantly reduce the need for specialised technical skills, lowering barriers to adoption for non-technical medical professionals and making digital tools more accessible to a wider range of healthcare professionals. This project is relevant given the ongoing digital health transformation and the increasing demand for solutions that are adaptable. By focusing on the role of LCNC platforms in healthcare, the research will address an underexplored area with the potential to drive meaningful, real-world change. The

outcomes of this project could pave the way for a more agile, user-driven approach to digital health innovation, ultimately improving both the adoption of digital solutions and the quality of patient care.

1.4 Aims and Objectives

The major aim of this project is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of selected LCNC platforms in enabling non-technical medical professionals to develop chronic disease management applications.

- To identify the LCNC platform used both in the industry and academia that offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing digital health applications for chronic disease management.
- To define the core features of a typical chronic disease management application through research, and to use these features to design a benchmark prototype that will serve as a reference for evaluating low-code/no-code platforms.
- To develop a chronic disease management app using each of the selected LCNC platforms.
- To assess, compare, and evaluate each platform using appropriate metrics from the perspective of non-technical medical professionals.
- To provide requirements for future LCNC development.

1.4.1 Research Questions

- Which LCNC platform offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing digital health applications for chronic disease management?
- How do selected LCNC platforms compare in terms of compliance with GDPR requirements, and ease of development for non-technical medical professionals?
- How intuitive and accessible are the GDPR-related features for non-technical medical professionals on each LCNC platform?
- What are the requirements of medical professionals when using low-code/no-code platforms to develop digital health applications?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction to Digital Health and Clinical Needs

The evolution of healthcare systems has been marked by steady progress from traditional paper-based record-keeping to sophisticated, intelligent digital health systems, reflecting a continuous and progressive transformation through advancements in technology. According to Shen et al. (2024), healthcare providers started keeping detailed paper records in the 19th century to track patients' medical records, treatments, and outcomes. Early attempts at digital transformation came in the 1960s with the adoption of electronic health records (Evans 2016). In recent years, digital health (mobile health (mHealth) and telehealth) applications emerged and grew rapidly, leveraging smartphones to enable remote patient monitoring and expand healthcare access beyond clinical settings (Bhatt et al. 2021; Chib and Lin 2018). Bhaskar et al. (2020) and Abdulaal et al. (2020) noted that the widespread use of mHealth during the COVID-19 pandemic significantly improved remote diagnostics and chronic disease support, demonstrating remote mHealth capabilities that enabled patient care both during and after COVID-19.

In the current decade, healthcare is characterised by the integration of cutting-edge technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Nasr et al. 2021), cloud computing (Ali et al. 2018), Internet of Things (IoT) (Baker et al. 2017), and big data analytics (Dash et al. 2019) into existing systems. Digital health innovations such as remote patient monitoring (RPM) systems, intelligent dashboards, and predictive decision systems are increasingly common in clinical settings (Shaik et al. 2023). Shaik et al. (2023) detailed how modern digital health tools have significantly enhanced chronic disease management, enabling continuous patient monitoring, early detection and intervention, real-time patient support, and personalised management of chronic conditions, thus marking a shift toward real-time, patient-centred care.

Dionisio et al. (2023) asserted that digital health has introduced numerous benefits, including improved access to healthcare, personalised treatment plans, and data-driven clinical decision-making. They further highlighted that digital interventions have remarkably improved operational workflows and patient outcomes, particularly within contexts of chronic care. Bhatt et al. (2021) corroborate that digital tools contributed to reductions in key health markers while promoting sustained remote care and better patient engagement.

Digital transformation is expected to be the key driver of improved clinical outcomes (Garg et al. 2005). But, despite these advances and benefits, the healthcare sector is evolving at a very slow pace (Sharma et al. 2019), the development of digital tools in healthcare remains hampered by complexity, cost, and compliance challenges. Creating compliant, secure, and user-friendly healthcare applications often exceeds the technical capacity of clinical teams, a gap that LCNC platforms are well-poised to fill by democratising app development and reducing dependence on specialist IT teams.

Scheibner et al. (2021) highlighted that the greatest challenge to digital health systems are ethico-legal factors such as privacy, informed and broad consent, and handling of data. These issues stem from compliance with regulatory bodies like the GDPR and HIPAA. They also point to technical shortcomings as one of the challenges faced. To develop compliant, functional, and user-friendly healthcare systems, these existing challenges must be addressed. In this context, LCNC platforms offer a promising solution. These platforms have the potential to significantly accelerate the development of healthcare applications by reducing reliance on traditional software engineering teams. LCNC platforms will also empower non-technical medical professionals with the ability to develop digital healthcare tools tailored to specific patient needs without requiring prior programming knowledge. As the healthcare sector continues to evolve rapidly, LCNC platforms may play a crucial role in healthcare innovation.

2.2 History and Principles of LCNC Platforms

The roots of LCNC platforms date back to early rapid application development tools and fourth-generation programming languages of the 1990s. However, the term "low-code" was first coined in 2014 by Forrester Research (Richardson and Rymer 2014).

LCNC platforms are visual development environments designed to enable users, often referred to as "citizen developers" to build software applications with minimal or no programming knowledge using visual interfaces, predefined components, and drag-and-drop workflows (Korada 2022). Da Cruz et al. (2021) highlight that although no-code and low-code could be used as synonyms, they are different concepts and can even target different user profiles. Low-code platforms may still require some coding for complex tasks, while no-code platforms abstract all coding entirely, relying on pre-built templates and logic builders instead (Korada 2022; Da Cruz et al. 2021).

LCNC platforms represent a transformational shift in software development used instead of, or in addition to conventional coding, enabling users to build applications with minimal or zero coding/programming knowledge (McLean 2021). According to Sanchis et al. (2019), due to the current digital transformation, different industries require robust tools to respond to dynamic & complex emerging needs and LCNC platforms have the potential to address these challenges. LCNC platforms support rapid, iterative, test-and-learn delivery and development (Richardson and Rymer 2014), enabling medical professionals to respond swiftly to evolving needs. According to a 2021 study by Gartner, LCNC platforms can reduce application development times by up to 90% compared to traditional methods. Alsaadi et al. (2021) analysed leading LCNC platforms such as OutSystems and Mendix and concluded that they transform business processes from time-consuming and labour-intensive manual processes to automated agile digital processes; demonstrating their potential to drastically reduce development cycles and significantly accelerate the delivery of health apps by automatically handling underlying technical complexities.

LCNC platforms have been heralded for democratising the app development process. Korada (2022) highlights that they bring power to non-technical users or “citizen developers”, which include medical professionals with domain expertise granting them the ability to build their own digital solutions tailored to specific needs. LCNC platforms have a role in reducing IT bottlenecks. Although medical professionals lack programming skills, abundant experience and knowledge in other fields like healthcare is present; since programming skills are hardly needed when using LCNC platforms, they could use the knowledge and experience to develop and maintain applications independently that meet specific niche use cases (Alsaadi et al. 2021).

In this era of digital transformation, the limited number of IT professionals makes it hard to manage all the evolving demands of businesses. In this situation, those who cannot get solutions from IT professionals would look for third-party solutions (Stangarone 2019). The emergence of LCNC platforms has relevance in such cases, where medical professionals can build tools tailored to patient and operational needs without the need for an IT team. This not only satisfies unique needs but also releases IT professionals from tedious work, enabling them to focus on more complex requirements (Yan 2021).

2.3 GDPR Relevance

The GDPR establishes a harmonised legal framework for the processing of personal data in the European Union and is the primary regulatory benchmark for this research. The GDPR’s principles and specific provisions shape how health-data applications must collect, process, secure, and disclose patient information; the following paragraphs summarise the particular Articles addressed in this study (Articles 5, 6, 7, 25 and 32) and explain their operational relevance to the design and evaluation of LCNC health applications. This study focuses on these GDPR articles because they directly relate to features that can be configured by non-technical users in LCNC platforms. Given the health context, these articles are especially important. Health data are special category data, triggering higher protection expectations and making minimisation, privacy-by-design, consent and robust security particularly critical at the application level. Focusing on these articles therefore targets the controls most immediately actionable by non-technical builders.

Article 5: Principles relating to processing of personal data

Article 5 codifies the core data-protection principles, including lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; and integrity and confidentiality (GDPR 2025). In practical terms for an application, Article 5 requires that only data strictly necessary for a stated purpose are collected, processed only for that purpose (or compatible purposes), stored only as long as necessary, and protected against unauthorised access or alteration. For health apps this means forms, data models and workflows must embody minimisation and purpose limitation from the outset.

Article 6: Lawfulness of processing

Article 6 specifies that processing of personal data is lawful only if at least one legal basis applies (consent, performance of a contract, or necessity for medical care) (GDPR 2025). For health applications, the common lawful bases are “processing necessary for provision of health care” and explicit consent for optional or secondary uses. Documenting which lawful basis applies to each processing activity is therefore an essential design requirement for health applications.

Article 7: Conditions for consent

Article 7 sets out requirements for valid consent (the controller must be able to demonstrate that the data subject consented) (GDPR 2025). This emphasises that consent under the GDPR must be freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous, and that controllers must be able to evidence consent and manage withdrawal. In health contexts, where consent is sometimes used for research or additional services, applications must capture consent metadata (who consented, and to what) and support effective withdrawal mechanisms consistent with the GDPR guidance.

Article 25: Data protection by design and by default

Article 25 requires controllers to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures so that, by default, only personal data necessary for each specific purpose are processed (GDPR 2025). This “privacy by design/default” obligation means that minimisation, default privacy-preserving settings, and role-based visibility should be embedded in the application architecture rather than left to ad-hoc configuration. For LCNC apps intended for non-technical medical professionals, the platform and the app templates should therefore make privacy the path of least resistance.

Article 32: Security of processing

Article 32 obliges controllers and processors to implement technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, explicitly listing measures such as pseudonymisation and encryption as examples, and requires consideration of the state of the art, cost, and processing context (GDPR 2025). For health applications (which routinely process special category health data), this translates into demonstrable encryption in transit and at rest (or equivalent protections), robust access controls (RBAC), and secure audit/logging that supports incident investigation. Supervisory guidance emphasises that security measures must be proportionate and documented as part of accountability obligations.

Health-care applications present a particularly high-risk profile because they process special-category data and are often integrated into clinical workflows. For an LCNC approach, the central research question becomes whether the platform’s built-in components and/or configuration options allow a

non-technical user to realise the Article-level requirements stated above without resorting to substantial developer intervention.

2.4 Opportunities and Benefits of LCNC Platforms for Medical Professionals

LCNC platforms offer considerable advantages in health app development by enabling rapid, cost effective, secure, and compliant domain-specific innovations, particularly for non-technical medical professionals.

As mentioned by Alsaadi et al. (2021) in their study, digital transformation is the transformative process of businesses from time-consuming and labour-intensive manual processes to automated agile digital processes. Yan (2021) further stated that for an industry to undergo digital transformation, they need a tool to improve development and delivery efficiency and LCNC platforms are one of the rising approaches to boost delivery speed. Richardson and Rymer (2014) reinforced this by stating that LCNC can speed up the applications development and delivery by 5-10 times and Gartner in their 2021 study corroborated this by stating that it can be up to 90% compared to traditional methods. For the healthcare industry where there are numerous conditions requiring numerous unique and tailored solutions, empowering the niche professionals with the ability to rapidly develop and deploy software without prior programming knowledge is essential. This speed is critical during emergencies when healthcare teams cannot afford project delays allowing them to continuously refine applications based on clinical feedback.

Siegler et al. (2021) in their study mentioned that one of the major challenges faced in developing mHealth interventions is the cost required to develop and maintain mobile apps. Melnik and Altynpara (2019) state that an app with few features can cost between US \$70,000 and \$100,000 and take 3-6 months to develop. Further stating that these costs mostly do not fit into the budget of funding bodies. The healthcare industry constantly has multiple digital solutions and innovations in the pipeline waiting to be developed upon, but a lack of funding hinders the commencement of these projects. Empowering medical professionals with LCNC platforms will drastically cut costs related to developing and deploying digital solutions, while ensuring that software produced is tailored to specific patient needs.

Stangarone (2019) and Yan (2021) in their studies highlight that LCNC platforms, when implemented and authorised correctly, can help solve the security and compliance risks. They further state that needed solutions can be built with the platforms without disturbing IT personnel. Since the application of data is being controlled properly, security, compliance, and privacy safety are guaranteed. If each component or building block in an LCNC platform is secure and optimised, the applications built with them should automatically be secure and optimised. Implementing LCNC platforms in healthcare has the potential to not only avoid security risks but also lessen the heavy testing workload compared to

the traditional development process. This ensures that medical professionals who are unskilled in implementing security protocols and compliance guidelines, can develop secure and compliant health apps tailored to specific needs.

2.5 Comparative review of Key LCNC Platforms

In the LCNC development industry, giant tech companies like Microsoft and Siemens have their own LCNC development platforms. Microsoft's OutSystems and Siemens's Mendix are widely recognised as leading enterprise-grade LCNC platforms.

OutSystems is a robust enterprise-focused low-code platform offering visual development with comprehensive full-stack and lifecycle management features. The focus of OutSystems is dedicated to developing applications that are used for automating core organisational processes for agile and continuous delivery (Alsaadi et al. 2021). OutSystems, while offering a robust visual development environment, often presents a steeper learning curve. It requires familiarity with development lifecycle concepts, such as component-based design and DevOps workflows, thus often necessitating hybrid teams of medical and IT professionals. It also excels in full-stack capability. For OutSystems, there are documented healthcare use cases. For example, Promedico built a medication-management and caregiver assistance apps in six weeks using the platform. Also, the NHS developed a new mobile app and a fully automated General Practitioner (GP) care system in less than 7 weeks using OutSystems (OutSystems 2024). These projects demonstrate rapid development and deployment and high adoption by clinical users, albeit with IT collaboration. (OutSystems 2022). OutSystems provides built-in support for HIPAA and GDPR compliance, featuring encryption, audit trails, secure deployment environments, and pre-deployment vulnerability scans, making it suitable for the healthcare sector where there are important compliance guidelines to follow.

Mendix is a full-stack LCNC platform supporting web and mobile app development via visual modelling and optional Java/JavaScript code. Reports by analysts like Gartner, IBM, and SAP recognised Mendix as a leading low-code development platform. Mendix offers strong support for citizen developers, enabling domain experts to participate in application building through drag-and-drop IDEs and guided templates. Mendix is frequently praised for being user-friendly, having an easier learning curve, however, mastering intricacies may require deeper technical know-how. The platform divides the design environment for citizen developers (an environment called Mendix Studio) and professional developers (Mendix Pro) for better collaborations between departments by providing suitable tools for people in different departments. Stakeholders can also cooperate with developers on the platform to provide in-time feedback to boost development and innovation (Alsaadi et al. 2021). Mendix enables robust backend logic via microflows with built-in support for cloud-native architectures and service integrations. In healthcare settings, Mendix empowers non-technical medical professionals to prototype tools rapidly. It has a built-in AI assistant that checks errors, inconsistencies, quality, and compliance and gives suggestions regarding the application being

built (Alsaadi et al. 2021). It can facilitate tasks like patient intake forms, appointment scheduling, and basic clinical workflows. Mendix includes essential compliance features, such as role-based access control, audit logging, and ISO/SOC certifications, making it feasible in the healthcare sector for non-technical medical professionals to build secure, compliant health applications

Criterion	Usability	Compliance and Security	Code Ownership	Backend Logic
OutSystems	Moderate: powerful visual tools but steeper learning curve, IT involvement needed on occasion.	HIPAA/GDPR support, vulnerability scanning, etc.	Full code ownership but very limited exportability, vendor lock-in.	Excellent
Mendix	High for citizen developers: some technical depth required.	SOC 2, ISO 27001, HIPAA/GDPR support, etc.	Full code ownership but limited exportability, vendor lock-in.	Strong: supports cloud-native workflows.

Table 1: Comparative review of LCNC platforms

2.6 Identified Research Gap

While LCNC platforms are increasingly adopted to accelerate software development across various sectors, there remains a significant gap in research examining their effectiveness and regulatory compliance ability within the context of healthcare application development by non-technical medical professionals. There is a lack of comparative analysis of widely adopted LCNC platforms such as OutSystems and Mendix against healthcare-specific requirements, including ease of implementation by medical professionals and alignment with data protection regulations like the GDPR. Furthermore, existing literature offers limited insight into how medical professionals themselves engage with and implement LCNC tools to build digital health applications. There is insufficient evidence identifying which LCNC platform is best suited for enabling non-technical medical professionals to develop effective and compliant health applications.

2.7 Conclusion

This literature review addresses the established gap by evaluating the capabilities of leading LCNC platforms through the lens of GDPR compliance, healthcare-specific use, and accessibility for non-technical medical professionals. By evaluating these platforms against healthcare-specific criteria and

involving non-technical personas in the process, this study aims to identify the most effective tools for empowering medical professionals to contribute directly to digital health innovation. Ultimately, the outcomes will inform future development practices, reduce dependency on technical teams, and accelerate the creation of compliant, secure healthcare applications.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

A research methodology serves as the comprehensive framework that guides the design, execution, and interpretation of a study. It encompasses the strategic choices researchers make, from defining objectives and selecting appropriate methods, to collecting and analysing data, ensuring that the study remains coherent, systematic, and rigorously executed (Rayshan 2025).

This research applies Design Science Research Methodology (DSRM) as articulated by Peffers et al. (2007), to design, develop and evaluate artefacts that address a practical information-systems problem: whether non-technical medical professionals can reasonably build GDPR-compliant health-care functionality using LCNC platforms. The artefact will consist of a comparative framework and prototype applications that assess the feasibility of medical professionals without advanced technical backgrounds using low-code platforms to develop compliance-ready health applications under selected provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, and 32). Over the past few decades, DSRM has emerged as a major paradigm characterizing most information system research that aims to design and implement innovative technologies intended to solve practical problems (Hevner and Chatterjee 2010). DSRM is particularly suited for building and evaluating digital healthcare artifacts (Schnall et al. 2014). The methodology operates through three interconnected cycles: relevance (understanding user context), design (creating the artifact), and rigor (evaluating against theory) (Myers and Venable 2014). This iterative process is exemplified in healthcare studies, where continuous refinement ensures contextual alignment.

According to Peffers et al. (2007), DSRM's value transcends artefact construction as it generates design knowledge, models, and theories that inform future practice and research.

The methodology simply offers a systematic framework to solving complex, real-world problems by designing and evaluating innovative artifacts (Hevner et al. 2004). Within the DSRM framework, this dissertation will follow the Peffers et al. (2007) six-step process.

3.2 Design Science Research Methodology

3.2.1 Problem Identification and Motivation

Healthcare professionals are increasingly exploring digital solutions to improve care delivery, including chronic disease management applications. However, the technical complexity of developing such applications, combined with strict data protection regulations like the GDPR, creates a substantial barrier for non-technical users. This is particularly acute when considering Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, and 32 of the GDPR, which focus on lawful processing, consent, privacy by design, and security of processing. The core problem at the heart of this

project is that medical professionals often need bespoke digital tools but lack software engineering skills to make them; at the same time, healthcare apps must meet strict data-protection standards (GDPR) and security requirements. The problem statement is therefore: Can LCNC platforms enable non-technical medical professionals to implement GDPR-relevant functionality (Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, 32) for a chronic-disease management application without developer support? Evidence shows that many mhealth apps fail critical compliance marks, for example an empirical analysis by Fan et al. (2020) revealed that 23.7% of the selected apps lacked complete privacy policies, and most had flawed data encryption protocols, highlighting the prevalence of GDPR non-compliance in mHealth contexts. Low-code environments can enable wider participation in app development but could lack embedded governance, raising risks around regulatory oversight as more non-technical users deploy solutions without structured compliance safeguards. This challenge is particularly acute in healthcare, where sensitive personal data is involved and compliance is non-negotiable.

3.2.2 Define Objectives of the Solution

The solution must establish compliance with particular articles of the GDPR as the key criteria. The objectives are derived from the problem and framed as measurable evaluation goals:

- A. Construct hybrid personas that realistically represent non-technical medical professionals' constraints and goals (time pressure, limited coding skills, compliance responsibility).
- B. Specify a benchmark chronic-disease app (minimum functionality) whose features concretely map to GDPR Articles 5, 6, 7, 25 and 32.
- C. Produce a comparative evaluation framework enabling transparent, repeatable assessment of two LCNC platforms (OutSystems and Mendix), measuring: Support (availability), Implementation Method, Ease of Implementation (effort), and Cost/Tier.
- D. Demonstrate and evaluate feature implementations on both platforms, producing reproducible evidence (build logs, screenshots, time metrics).

3.2.3 Design and development

In this phase, two distinct prototypes will be developed, one on OutSystems and one on Mendix. These artifacts must include workflows aligned with GDPR Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, and 32 and meet the objectives defined in Step 2. It will build the tangible components used in the demonstration and evaluation.

Key activities will include:

A. Hybrid personas

Each persona is documented with role, technical proficiency, goals, pain points, and compliance concerns. Personas are grounded in literature and anecdotal accounts from practicing medical professionals. The personas function as the “user lens” for simulated builds, that is, the researcher acts while constrained by the persona’s skills.

B. Benchmark application specification

A concise specification of the chronic-disease app is produced (core features only). Applicable features are explicitly mapped to relevant GDPR Articles.

C. Considerations for LCNC Platform

In parallel with the benchmark application design, the research also benchmarks the LCNC platforms themselves. This determines the required properties the chosen LCNC platforms (OutSystems and Mendix) must possess.

3.2.4 Demonstration

The benchmark application will be built separately on OutSystems and Mendix. For each GDPR-linked scenario the researcher demonstrates the implementation in both platforms: Demonstrations focus on discrete, testable tasks (create a consent form, create a delete account button).

Each demonstration session is recorded as a build log with: step-by-step actions and annotated screenshots capturing configuration screens, logic flows (microflows/server actions), and final app views. Screenshots are taken at pre-defined key states: initial configuration screen, intermediate logic builder showing how the function works, final app UI, and any platform audit/log outputs that provide compliance evidence.

3.2.5 Evaluation

The evaluation phase assesses the feasibility of implementing selected GDPR compliance features in each LCNC platform when used by a non-technical medical professional (represented via a hybrid persona). The goal is not to compare the overall power of the platforms in software engineering terms, but to measure their suitability for enabling compliant app development in healthcare contexts.

3.2.5.1 Metrics for Evaluation

Support (feature availability)

Does the platform provide the required feature in a usable form?

- Built-in (Score = 3): Feature exists as a discoverable, documented UI capability (point-and-click). No custom code or external services required.

- Partial (Light Configuration) (Score = 2): Feature is achievable but requires non-trivial configuration, marketplace components/plugins, or light scripting (microflows/server actions).
- Partial (Moderate Configuration) (Score = 1): Feature is achievable but requires more extensive setup or modification to be compliant.
- Not supported (Score = 0): Feature is not practicable within the platform without substantial custom development or vendor interventions.

Ease of Implementation (Effort rating)

How much effort would a realistic non-technical medical professional need to implement this feature?

- Low Effort (Score = 2): ≤ 15 minutes using visual tools only; no custom code.
- Partial Effort (Score = 1): 15-60 minutes; may require light custom logic or extensive configuration.
- High Effort (Score = 0): > 60 minutes; likely requires technical knowledge, external resources like API integrations, or enterprise features.

Auditability

Does the platform produce tamper-evident logs and records that substantiate compliance claims?

- Built-in (Score = 3): Platform provides discoverable, documented audit-trail functionality. No developer code required.
- Partial (Light Configuration) (Score = 2): Platform supports audit trails but requires light configuration or marketplace modules.
- Partial (Moderate Configuration) (Score = 1): Auditability achievable only by implementing custom logging entities and server logic
- Not Supported (Score = 0): No practical mechanism to capture timestamped processing logs without substantial development or external services.

Cost / Tier Requirement

Does the implementation require a paid tier, enterprise plan, or is it available in the free/community edition?

Required Evidence

Build logs: Textual, sequential record of steps.

Time-on-task: Measured from task start to successful completion or abandonment.

Screenshots: Annotated images of key states (configuration pages, logic editors, final app screens).

Scoring protocol: For each feature/platform, record Support (0-3), Ease of Implementation (0-2), Auditability (0-3), and Cost/Tier.

3.2.5.2 Analysis plan

The analysis will evaluate each LCNC platform against the GDPR-relevant compliance features using the hybrid personas. For each feature-platform combination, three core measures will be recorded: Ease of Implementation (EI), Auditability, and Support. Support will indicate whether the feature was implemented with features the LCNC platform provides. EI will reflect the level of effort required, capturing the time on each task implementation. And Auditability will show if the platform can generate, retain, and export logs that demonstrate GDPR-relevant actions. These measures will be combined into a Compliance Implementation Score (CIS) to enable direct comparison across platforms.

Descriptive statistics (counts) will summarise EI, Support, Auditability, and CIS for each platform and GDPR article. Qualitative data from the build logs and annotated screenshots will be thematically analysed to identify recurring barriers, enablers, and contextual factors influencing implementation. These qualitative insights will be used to explain observed quantitative differences and highlight real-world constraints such as enterprise-only features or technical dependencies.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings will produce a practical classification of each feature as (1) feasible with low effort, (2) feasible but constrained, or (3) not feasible for non-technical users. This mixed-methods approach will ensure that conclusions are both statistically grounded and contextually meaningful.

3.2.6 Communication

Findings from the research will be presented in a detailed research report as a framework in the dissertation. This framework will be synthesised into design-guidance for medical personnel considering LCNC platforms. This step promotes the distribution of knowledge and application of the solution.

By positioning this comparative study within the DSR framework, the research not only aims to build clinician-driven LCNC artifacts but majorly to extract insights about platform suitability and compliance. It thereby contributes to both academic knowledge on design processes and practical guidance for healthcare innovation.

3.3 Methodological Approach to Research Questions

The study's methodology was designed to ensure that each research question was systematically addressed through appropriate evaluation activities. The alignment is summarised below:

Research Question	Alignment
Which low-code/no-code (LCNC) platform offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing digital health applications for chronic disease management?	A structured selection of two widely adopted platforms (Mendix and OutSystems) was undertaken based on academic and industry references. A benchmark prototype for chronic disease management was then implemented in both platforms. Effectiveness was assessed using the Compliance Implementation Score (CIS), which combined feature support and ease of implementation, thereby providing a comparative measure of platform suitability.
How do selected LCNC platforms compare in terms of compliance with GDPR requirements, and ease of development for non-technical medical professionals?	GDPR Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, and 32 were operationalised into evaluation tasks (data minimisation, lawful-basis gating, consent capture/withdrawal, privacy-by-design, and security of processing). For each platform, tasks were implemented in the prototype and scored using the Support and Ease of Implementation (EI) scales. This created a standardised basis for comparison of compliance coverage and development effort.
How intuitive and accessible are the GDPR-related features for non-technical medical professionals on each LCNC platform?	To approximate the experience of non-technical users, a constrained persona was adopted, limiting implementation actions to those feasible without coding expertise. During prototype building, observations were recorded. These provided indicators of intuitiveness and accessibility, even though direct testing with medical professionals was outside the project's scope.
What are the requirements of medical professionals when using low-code/no-code platforms to develop digital health applications?	A literature review of chronic disease management applications, digital health adoption studies, and regulatory guidance was used to derive functional and compliance-oriented requirements. These were embedded in the benchmark prototype and served as evaluation criteria against which the platforms were assessed.

Table 2: Methodological approach to research questions

3.4 Gantt Chart

The Gantt chart, a visual tool for planning and tracking projects, was developed in the early 20th century by mechanical engineer Henry L. Gantt (Wilson 2000). It will be employed to strategize and

oversee this project by outlining the project's objectives, establishing tasks and milestones, and predicting the duration of each work. Below is the gantt chart used for this project:

Figure 1: Gantt chart

3.5 Risk Assessment

Risk	Impact	Likelihood	Severity	Mitigation Strategy
Delay with Prototype Design	5	3	15	Start the design process early, allocate extra time for learning, and seek assistance from peers or supervisors.
Delay with LCNC implementation	5	3	15	Start LCNC implementation early, allocate extra time for learning, seek assistance from peers or supervisors.
Informed Consent and Ethical Considerations	5	2	10	Provide clear, detailed information to participants, obtain written consent, and ensure ethical approval before starting.
Health Issues of Researcher	5	5	25	Maintain a balanced schedule, seek medical advice promptly, and have contingency plans for project tasks.

Data Loss	5	2	10	Regularly back up data to secure locations such as cloud storage and external drives.
Time Constraints	4	3	12	Develop a detailed project timeline, prioritize tasks, and maintain a balanced schedule.

Table 3: Risk assessment

3.6 Ethical Consideration

The low-risk project, approved by Dr. Sofia Meacham **on April 22, 2024**, began on the 19th of May, 2025. The project follows ethical guidelines, ensuring confidentiality and privacy where required. Participants are informed they can exit the study without explanation, and the researcher has no influence over them or the methodology.

4 REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

In the digital realm, healthcare or software and systems engineering, requirements analysis is the critical process by which stakeholder needs are clarified, documented, validated, and managed. It serves as the foundation for the ensuing design and development phases, ensuring that the final product aligns with research expectations and goals. Flores et al. (2009) define it as the process of discovering the purpose of the software system by identifying stakeholders and their needs, and documenting these in a form that is amenable to analysis, communication, and subsequent implementation.

4.1 User Personas

A user persona is a carefully crafted, fictitious archetype representing a segment of real users, distilled from qualitative data and research insights. Personas encapsulate users' goals, behaviours, motivations, and constraints, enabling teams to empathize with and work effectively for their target audience. Ferreira et al. (2018) define it simply as a hypothetical archetype of a real user that describes the user's goals, skills, and interests. These personas, based on literature review and requirement gathering, are visually represented below:

Figure 2: Medical doctor user persona

Figure 3: Nurse user persona

Figure 4: Medical researcher user persona

4.2 Considerations for the Low-Code/No-Code Platform

The adoption of Low-Code/No-Code (LCNC) platforms in the healthcare sector addresses critical gaps in digital health accessibility, particularly for non-technical medical professionals.

The selection of LCNC platforms for this research is grounded in their alignment with core criteria necessary for development of GDPR-compliant healthcare applications led by medical professionals.

These platforms must balance a robust set of features to allow medical professionals design and implement health applications without extensive programming knowledge: enterprise-grade security, built-in/configurable compliance controls, ease of implementation for non-technical users, and flexibility to implement key GDPR workflows without traditional coding.

Security and compliance are paramount for LCNC platforms in healthcare settings, given the sensitive nature of patient data and the regulatory frameworks such as the GDPR required for its protection. According to Knorr and Aspinall (2015), security is a significant concern due to health-critical data privacy and integrity. Hussain et al. (2018) says that most digital health apps have not fully implemented security mechanisms to protect the health data of patients, and a large part of this security relies on the development process (Aljedaani and Babar 2021). These platforms must comply with regulatory bodies for patient data. Two of the most prominent regulatory bodies are HIPAA in the US and GDPR in the EU, which provide guidelines for safeguarding patient privacy and ensure the secure handling of patient health information (Reddy and Immaneni 2021). The platforms must comply with selected important articles: Article 5 (principles relating to processing of personal data), 6 (lawfulness of processing), 7 (conditions for consent), 25 (data protection by design and by default) and 32 (security of processing) of the GDPR regulations. The selection of an LCNC platform for healthcare applications must be guided by its ability to meet stringent security and compliance standards. Platforms that offer built-in compliance with regulations like GDPR and HIPAA, along with robust security features such as encryption, RBAC, are essential for safeguarding patient data and maintaining regulatory adherence. This eliminates the need for additional configuration or engineering work to meet compliance standards.

With the advent of digital transformation not only in healthcare but in every industry, usability (ease in implementation) is a critical consideration for evaluating LCNC platforms in healthcare. According to Beranič et al. (2020), a major advantage of using a LCNC platform is an intuitive interface and easy to use design. Mohammadkhani et al. (2025) in their study also identified that LCNC platforms typically provide a graphical interface where users can drag and drop components, automate workflows, and configure settings to design applications instead of writing extensive manual code from scratch. Khalajzadeh and Grundy (2025) emphasise that this may exclude users with visual impairments due to their reliance on graphical interfaces, therefore, LCNC platforms must address these concerns and prioritize usability to ensure seamless use amongst medical professionals.

In summary, the implementation of Low-Code/No-Code platforms within the healthcare domain requires a thorough understanding of the platform's capabilities, especially when applied to the development of applications for chronic disease management. As established through the reviewed literature, core requirements such as security and regulatory compliance, high ease of implementation, and robust compatibility across multiple devices constitute essential considerations for evaluating the effectiveness of LCNC platforms in this domain.

These features serve not only as criteria for assessing the strengths and limitations of various LCNC platforms for this project, but also as a guide for ensuring that the tools developed through these platforms are viable in real-world healthcare environments. They will form the basis for the comparative analysis in the subsequent stages of this project. This foundation ensures that the resulting assessment is both contextually grounded and practically relevant for future digital health implementations.

4.3 Benchmark features for the Chronic Disease management App

Developing a benchmark application sets the foundation for rigorous comparative evaluation. By specifying a consistent set of core features such as consent recording, data minimisation, data deletion, and access controls, the research ensures that any differences observed across Mendix and OutSystems are attributable to platform capability, rather than design variation. Without this common baseline, comparisons would lack standardization and validity, making it impossible to draw robust conclusions about which platform better supports GDPR implementation for non-technical medical professionals.

An ideal chronic disease management application should encompass several key features to effectively support patients and healthcare providers. These features are grounded in current research and best practices in the field of digital health.

1. Health Data Monitoring:

The continuous monitoring of health metrics such as blood glucose levels and blood pressure is fundamental in managing many chronic conditions. The Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2024) highlights the importance of remote patient monitoring (RPM) in chronic disease management, noting that electronic devices can record a patient's health data for providers to evaluate, facilitating timely interventions and personalised care. Mao et al. (2020) in their study emphasised that mHealth interventions, including remote monitoring, significantly improved clinical outcomes for patients with chronic conditions like diabetes. Similarly, Serrano et al. (2023) emphasised that real-time monitoring of patients could improve management of chronic conditions like hypertension and diabetes and reduce hospital readmissions. Ma et al (2022) then explains its effectiveness by facilitating regular follow-ups. Given the existing literature, it is a prerequisite that an ideal chronic disease management application can monitor and transmit patient health data, facilitating early detection of anomalies, supporting personalised interventions, and empowering patients in self-management.

2. Medication Management:

Effective medication management is a cornerstone in the treatment of chronic diseases, as adherence to prescribed medication significantly influences patient outcomes. Non-adherence

can lead to disease progression, increased hospitalizations, and higher healthcare costs. Digital health interventions, particularly mobile applications, have emerged as promising tools to enhance medication adherence among patients with chronic conditions (Kim et al. 2025). Furthermore, Kim et al. (2025) in their systematic review and meta-analysis assessed the effectiveness of mobile health interventions on medication adherence in patients with chronic diseases. They concluded that mobile applications significantly improved medication adherence rates compared to standard care, highlighting the potential of these digital tools in chronic disease management. Similarly, Hartch et al. (2023) evaluated the impact of a smartphone application on medication adherence among populations with various chronic illnesses. The intervention group using the app demonstrated significantly greater medication adherence and self-efficacy compared to the control group, suggesting that mobile apps can effectively support medication management in diverse populations. This highlights that incorporating robust medication management features into chronic disease management applications is essential.

3. User Profile Management:

User profile management in chronic disease management applications allows patients to create and maintain individualized health profiles. These profiles store critical demographic data like (age, sex), medical history (diagnoses, medications, allergies), lifestyle factors, and user preferences. Such comprehensive data collection is essential for delivering personalised care and facilitating effective management strategies. A study by D'Antrassi et al. (2016) proposed a comprehensive architecture for mHealth systems aimed at enhancing patient participation in their care process. The study emphasised the importance of integrating technical and psychological/clinical needs through personalised solutions, highlighting the role of user profiles in achieving this integration. Furthermore, Wang et al. (2025) conducted a study on designing adaptive user interfaces for mHealth applications targeting chronic diseases. The research highlighted the necessity of tailoring interfaces to specific individual user needs, which inherently relies on detailed user profiles.

4. User-Friendly Interface:

A user-friendly interface is a pivotal component in the design of chronic disease management applications, as it directly influences user engagement, adherence, and overall effectiveness of the digital health intervention. It is essential to ensure that the app is accessible and easy to navigate for users with varying levels of technical proficiency, including older adults and those with disabilities. Wang et al. (2022) suggests that adaptive user interfaces that change or can be changed to accommodate the user and usage context differences in chronic disease applications have been found to improve usability and reduce user frustration. A user-friendly interface is not merely an aesthetic consideration but a fundamental aspect of chronic disease management applications.

5. Personalised Educational Content:

Personalised educational content is an important feature in chronic disease management applications, as it empowers patients with tailored information that aligns with their specific health conditions. Cucciniello et al. (2021) conducted a systematic review on characteristics of mobile health apps in the management of chronic conditions, concluding that personalised content was a major feature and it improved patient engagement and self-management behaviours. This customization enhances patient engagement by delivering tailored information that aligns with individual patient needs and preferences. These applications can then effectively support patients in managing their chronic conditions.

5 DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT

5.1 Design Rationale

The design of this framework was driven by the need to evaluate whether LCNC platforms can enable non-technical medical professionals to implement data protection and privacy requirements mandated by the GDPR in health application development. While LCNC platforms promise accessibility and rapid prototyping (Richardson and Rymer 2014), their adequacy for compliance with stringent healthcare regulations remains underexplored.

The framework therefore operationalises selected GDPR Articles. These provisions were selected because they represent directly actionable requirements within application design, as opposed to organisational or contractual obligations outside the builder's control. By grounding the framework in these five articles, the design prioritises practical implementability within LCNC tools while ensuring alignment with the most salient regulatory requirements for healthcare applications.

5.2 Framework Construction

The framework was designed as an evaluation tool comprising three key dimensions: Support, Auditability, and Ease of Implementation (EI). Each metric was assigned a scale, and these were combined into a Composite Implementation Score (CIS), which provides a simple measure of each platform's overall suitability for non-technical GDPR-aligned application building.

5.3 Prototype Development (LCNC Role)

While the framework is the artefact of this research, prototype builds in Mendix and OutSystems served as testbeds for applying and validating the framework. These prototypes simulated a chronic-disease management app functions directly linked to GDPR obligations. The app screens and their GDPR-related function is handled later in this study.

5.4 Evaluation Setup

The evaluation process applied the framework systematically:

- **Operationalisation of GDPR criteria:** each article was translated into measurable features.
- **Application in LCNC platforms:** prototypes were configured in both Mendix and OutSystems by adhering to the “non-technical medical professional” persona.
- **Evidence collection:** where necessary, screenshots, logs, configuration states, and workflow mappings were captured to support scoring decisions.
- **Scoring:** each feature was assessed on Support, Auditability, and EI, generating a CIS per article per platform.

5.5 Prototype Screens and GDPR Compliance Mapping

This section presents selected screenshots from the app to show how key workflows operationalize the GDPR requirements addressed in this study: Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, and 32. Screens not critical to the compliance argument are omitted here for clarity. Where a control is not fully visible in the UI (encryption at rest/in transit), the accompanying text explicitly notes the control.

5.5.1 Sign Up Screen

The signup screen initiates the service relationship and records the minimum identifiers required to open an account (email, password). Processing here is lawful under Article 6(1)(b) because creating and operating the account is necessary for the performance of a contract (access to the app's core services). By limiting fields to essentials and omitting optional demographics, the design demonstrates Article 5(1)(c) data minimisation, implemented by default in the form structure (Article 25). Submission and storage occur over secure transport and platform-managed storage, aligning with Article 32.

The image shows a mobile application sign-up screen. At the top, the title "Sign Up" is centered in a large, bold, black font. Below the title, the subtitle "Create an account and explore" is centered in a smaller, regular black font. The form consists of three input fields: "Email", "Password", and "Confirm Password". Each field is a rounded rectangle with a thin black border. The "Password" field includes a small eye icon on the right side to toggle visibility. Below the input fields is a prominent green button with the text "Sign Up" in white. Underneath the button, the word "OR" is centered in a small, grey font. Below "OR" are three social login options, each in a rounded rectangle: "Continue with Google" with the Google logo, "Continue with Facebook" with the Facebook logo, and "Continue with Apple" with the Apple logo. At the bottom of the screen, the text "Already have an account? Login" is displayed, with "Login" being a blue hyperlink.

Figure 5: Sign up screen

5.5.2 Login Screen

The login screen enforces confidentiality and integrity of personal data by authenticating the user before any record access, illustrating Article 32. Security-by-default controls (masked passwords, previous session timeout) reflect Article 25, ensuring protective measures are embedded in the default runtime configuration rather than relying on user discretion. It also aligns with Article 6(1)(b) as it is necessary for further performance of a contract.

Login

Welcome Back! You've been missed!

Email

Password

Login

OR

Continue with Google

Continue with Facebook

Continue with Apple

Don't have an account? [Sign up](#)

Figure 6: Login screen

5.5.3 Personal Information Screen

This screen captures core identity data strictly necessary to operate the account and provide the service; processing is lawful under Article 6(1)(b). The input sections implement data minimisation

(Art. 5(1)(c)), while supporting accuracy (Art. 5(1)(d)) and reflect privacy-by-default at the point of capture (Art. 25). Data transfer and storage are secured per Article 32.

The image shows a mobile application screen with a white background and rounded corners, framed by a thick black border. At the top, the title "Personal Information" is centered in a bold, black font. Below the title are four vertically stacked input fields, each with a light gray border and rounded ends. The labels for these fields are "Full Name", "Date of Birth", "Gender", and "Contact", positioned to the left of each input box. At the bottom of the screen, there is a prominent green button with rounded corners and the word "Next" centered in white text.

Figure 7: Personal information screen

5.5.4 Medical Information Screen

For the app, collecting only clinically relevant health attributes is necessary to perform the service, grounding Article 6(1)(b). The screen constrains data capture to required clinical fields, evidencing minimisation (Art. 5(1)(c)) and embeds validation for accuracy (Art. 5(1)(d)). Layout and visibility rules demonstrate privacy-by-default (Art. 25), and platform security controls meet Article 32.

The image shows a mobile application screen titled "Medical Information". It features four input fields: "Weight (kg)", "Height (cm)", "Diagnoses", and "Medication". The "Diagnoses" field contains the text "Diabetes". At the bottom of the screen is a green button labeled "Next".

Figure 8: Medical information screen

5.5.5 Emergency Contact Screen

Emergency contact data is processed to protect the vital interests of the data subject in urgent situations, satisfying Article 6(1)(d). The design limits collection to essential attributes (name, relationship, phone) to meet minimisation (Art. 5(1)(c)). By default, it avoids optional or intrusive fields, demonstrating privacy-by-default (Art. 25), and the usual transport/storage protections address Article 32.

The image shows a mobile application screen titled "Emergency Contact". It features three input fields: "Contact Name", "Relationship", and "Phone Number", each with a rounded rectangular border. Below these fields is a prominent green button with the text "Next" in white. The entire screen is enclosed in a thick black border, representing the phone's frame.

Figure 9: Emergency contact screen

5.5.6 Privacy Policy Screen

This screen presents clear, specific information about processing and requires an explicit, opt-in action (toggle on) to proceed where consent is the chosen lawful basis, implementing Articles 7 and 6(1)(a). The policy text and link address fairness/transparency (Art. 5(1)(a)). The toggle which is turned off by default embodies privacy-by-default (Art. 25). The system stores evidence of consent (status, timestamp). Secure submission fulfils Article 32.

Figure 10: Privacy policy screen

5.5.7 Monitor Screen

Ongoing self-monitoring and medication logging are core to the contracted service (Art. 6(1)(b)). The screen limits inputs to necessary measurements and medication details, evidencing minimisation (Art. 5(1)(c)). By constraining fields and excluding unrelated attributes, it operationalizes privacy-by-default (Art. 25). Secured storage/transit address Article 32 for integrity and confidentiality.

Figure 11: Monitor screen

5.5.8 Profile Screen

Providing a consolidated, editable view enables users to review and correct their information, supporting accuracy (Art. 5(1)(d)) and transparency (Art. 5(1)(a)). The profile shows only data necessary for app function (no over-exposure), maintaining minimisation (Art. 5(1)(c)) and privacy-by-default (Art. 25). Access is restricted to the authenticated user (and not displayed to other roles), aligning with Article 32.

Figure 12: Profile screen

5.5.9 Settings Screen

This screen implements the app decision that withdrawing consent = account deletion. When the user confirms deletion, the system ceases processing (Art. 6) and performs erasure/pseudonymisation consistent with storage limitation (Art. 5(1)(e)). Placing deletion visibly in Settings satisfies privacy-by-design/default (Art. 25) by making withdrawal practical, not buried. The operation should perform secure deletion steps in line with Article 32.

Figure 13: Settings screen

6 FINDINGS

This study aims to present the empirical results of evaluating whether LCNC platforms: OutSystems and Mendix enable non-technical medical professionals to implement GDPR-relevant functionality for a health application. The focus is feasibility for non-technical builders, not a full technical benchmark of platform performance. The analysis concentrates on GDPR Articles 5 (principles of data processing), 6 (lawfulness), 7 (conditions for consent), 25 (data protection by design and by default), and 32 (security of processing) as shown in the app's core features (consent capture and withdrawal via account deletion, data minimisation in registration and monitoring, RBAC, and encryption).

Findings are presented thematically, using the evaluation metrics defined in the Methodology: Support (feature availability in a usable form), Auditability (criteria for recording) and Ease of Implementation (EI) (effort required by a realistic non-technical builder). Where helpful for context, Cost/Tier requirements are noted, but the primary basis for comparison is the composite Compliance Implementation Score (CIS) derived from the sum of Support, Auditability, and EI (as specified in the Methodology). Results are evidenced with build logs, measured time-on-task, and annotated screenshots that document configuration states (role/permission settings), logic editors (microflows/server actions), and the resulting app screens.

The data analysed comprise:

- I. Prototype builds on both platforms following the hybrid personas that constrain the researcher to non-technical actions.
- II. Platform documentation consulted during implementation.
- III. The GDPR feature-compliance checks embedded in the benchmark specification.

To maintain clarity and traceability, this chapter organises results by GDPR article and feature, reporting Support, Auditability, and EI for each platform, followed by cross-cutting themes that emerge across them. For each theme, findings are presented separately for Mendix and OutSystems across two key dimensions: Platform Support, Auditability, and Ease of Implementation (EI). These were scored on a 0-3, 0-3, and 0-2 scale respectively based on the evaluation framework developed in Chapter 3. A Compliance Implementation Score (CIS) was then derived by summing them, providing an integrated measure of each platform's overall suitability.

6.1 Theme A; Article 5: Principles relating to processing of personal data

Non-technical builders must be able to limit data collection to what is necessary and restrict access by role. This was operationalised at two points: registration (separate screens for Personal Information, Medical Information, Emergency Contact) limited to fields strictly required for a chronic-disease application; and monitoring (input of only essential physiological measures and medication

entries). Field-level validation was used to ensure only essential attributes were collected, and optional fields were deliberately excluded to avoid collecting non-essential data. They must also be able to ensure accountability/auditability, meaning that system actions (record creation, updates, deletions, access events) can be logged and retrieved as evidence.

Mendix (Support: 2; EI: 1; Auditability = 2; CIS = 5)

Mendix provides visual form designers and domain modelling that make it straightforward to define which fields are required and which are optional, and to restrict visibility of fields by role. For the app, these capabilities were immediately usable with little configuration. However, audit logging requires either configuration of the Audit Trail Module from the Mendix Marketplace, or building custom logging logic. This setup involves navigating multiple configuration screens and understanding entity associations; a light barrier for non-technical builders. This was feasible with low effort for mendix.

OutSystems (Support: 2; EI: 1; Auditability = 2; CIS = 5)

OutSystems offers comparable visual tools for form creation, validation and basic page-level access control. The platform supports slightly better conditional visibility and simple rules without custom coding for the study use-case. Where it diverges is auditability; OutSystems has no audit logging module but has some level of application logging available by default, with light setup needed. Simple audit trails can be enabled with minimal configuration. This was also feasible with low effort for outsystems.

Cost / Tier

Both platforms support these basic features in free tiers; no enterprise add-ons are required for the simple data-minimisation patterns used here.

Data minimisation is fully feasible on both platforms and imposes low effort for a non-technical builder. Differences are largely in interface layout and discoverability rather than capability. While both platforms support audit trails with similar levels of effort, they implement them through different patterns.

Implementation screens supporting Article 5 are provided in figures 7, 8, and 9.

6.2 Theme B; Article 6: Lawfulness of processing

The legal basis (consent or contractual necessity) must be identified and no processing until a lawful basis exists. Lawfulness was anchored in performance of a contract for service provision at signup (account creation) and reinforced by explicit consent for processing via the privacy screen. Access to functionality was gated until a legal basis was established. The auditability assessment focused on whether the platform records legal-basis status and logs the timestamp when the basis was asserted.

Mendix (Support: 2; EI: 1; Auditability = 2; CIS = 3)

Mendix allows modeling of acceptance and simple navigation checks. Implementing these requires modest configuration (define the attribute, add conditional navigation), which is accessible to non-technical users with minimal effort. The audit module can be configured to record acceptance actions, though more granular consent-event tracking requires extra steps not handled in the study.

This was feasible with low effort for mendix.

OutSystems (Support: 2; EI: 1; Auditability = 2; CIS = 3)

OutSystems supports equivalent patterns. Setting up the requirements is not a one-click feature, but it is achievable via visual configuration with light effort. Logging of legal-basis actions is supported but requires some technical intervention for detailed tracking. This was also feasible with low effort for outsystems.

Cost / Tier

Basic support in free tiers.

Both platforms enable lawful-basis gating with light configuration.

Figure 14: Flow of enabling consent check before app progress (Mendix)

Figure 15: Flow of enabling consent check before app progress (Outsystems)

6.3 Theme C; Article 7: Conditions for consent (capture and withdrawal)

Where consent is relied upon, it must be obtained explicitly, and withdrawal must be allowed. Consent is captured via a switch and enforced as a gate to functionality. Withdrawal of consent is implemented as account deletion (the user chooses to stop using the service; the account and associated data are deleted). For this theme auditability was evaluated by (a) whether consent metadata (boolean, timestamp) are logged, and (b) whether withdrawal events (delete account) generate auditable records that demonstrate the user action.

Mendix (Support: 1; EI: 1; Auditability = 2; CIS = 4)

Mendix supports capturing consent and offers the means to implement deletion workflows. The deletion workflow required more than light configuration but was still tractable. This was feasible but constrained for mendix.

OutSystems (Support: 1; EI: 0.5; Auditability = 1; CIS = 2.5)

OutSystems provides the same basic building blocks. Components exist that can streamline consent handling, but delete-account required heavier configuration than in Mendix to reach the same end-state, pushing the effort into the high category for a non-technical builder. This was barely feasible and very constrained for outsystems. This bordered on being not feasible for non-technical builders.

Cost / Tier

Basic consent capture is available in free tiers.

Consent capture is straightforward; withdrawal via deletion is the most burdensome feature for non-technical users. Mendix is somewhat easier but still non-trivial. It requires careful configuration to ensure cascade deletion. Outsystems on the other hand, required a lot of logic.

Figures 14 and 15 highlight the consent workflow.

Figure 16: Cascade deletion workflow (Mendix)

Figure 17: Total account deletion (Mendix)

Figure 18: Retrieve user account for deletion (Outsystems)

Figure 19: Initial account deletion process (Outsystems)

Figure 20: Final account deletion process (Outsystems)

6.4 Theme D; Article 25: Data protection by design and by default

Secure-by-default settings, role-based access, and design-time rules that prevent over-collection/exposure are necessary. Privacy by design/default was addressed by: default-deny navigation until legal basis is set; least-privilege roles defined at design time and applied to pages/entities; and minimal default forms and no collection of non-essential data. For auditability, this study did not implement an internal configuration logging mechanism to capture design-time privacy decisions. While these decisions were made and enforced within the application, they were not tracked in a structured or persistent manner. As a result, the auditability of these choices under Article 25, particularly the ability to evidence 'privacy by design' decisions, is limited in the current prototype.

Mendix (Support: 3; EI: 2; CIS = 3)

Mendix's model-level access control and page permissions make privacy-by-default achievable through configuration. Once roles and access are defined, they can be applied consistently across the model. This was feasible with very low effort in mendix.

OutSystems (Support: 3; EI: 2; CIS = 3)

OutSystems similarly supports design-time role definitions and screen access rules. This was also feasible with very low effort for outsystems.

Cost / Tier

Core design-time access controls are available for free.

Both platforms allow privacy to be embedded at design time.

Name	Module roles
Administrator	System.Administrator, Administration.Administrator, MyFirstModule.User
Patient	System.User, MyFirstModule.Patient

Figure 21: Selecting roles access (Mendix)

Figure 22: Selecting roles access (Outsystems)

6.5 Theme E; Article 32: Security of processing

Platforms must provide secure transport, secure storage and logging options. Security relied on platform-managed controls: TLS in transit, encryption at rest, and platform authentication. For auditability, the auditability assessment considered both the existence of security-related logs (logins, failed logins, user session) and the accessibility of those logs for incident investigation. The platforms provided some basic level of security-related logging automatically.

Mendix (Support: 3; EI: 2; Auditability = 3; CIS = 5)

Mendix Cloud and platform documentation indicate standard security measures; these are enabled by default in managed deployments and require little to no configuration for the app. The prototype relied on managed-cloud defaults for Art.32 so this is provided by default across platforms.

OutSystems (Support: 3; EI: 2; Auditability = 3; CIS = 5)

OutSystems managed environments likewise provide secure transport and storage defaults.

Cost / Tier

Fundamental security features are included in the free version.

For an app built on managed low-code platforms, basic Article 32 expectations are met by platform defaults.

Taken together, these results indicate that both platforms enable a GDPR-aligned application for chronic disease management without paid tiers, but they do so with different friction points for non-technical builders. OutSystems exhibited an advantage for rapid form construction and field-level

controls (Article 5), which translated into lower observed effort at the data minimisation touchpoints. Mendix, by contrast, proved more congenial for consent-gating conceptually linked to Articles 6 and 7, even though consent withdrawal via “delete account” still demanded more than light configuration on both platforms and remained the single most effort-intensive feature. Auditability through these themes required light to moderate configuration to set up.

Across Articles 25 and 32, the platforms were functionally equivalent: design-time roles, page access rules, secure transport and storage, and for auditability, basic logging are built-in defaults that require little app-layer work. This suggests that, for non-technical builders, platform defaults do the heavy lifting for privacy-by-default and baseline security; the builder’s main task is to apply those defaults consistently (Article 25) and document them credibly (Article 32).

Cost/tier considerations did not differentiate the platforms at this scope; all implemented features were achievable on free editions.

Theme/ GDPR Article	Mendix Support	Mendix EI	Mendix Auditability	Mendix CIS	OutSystems Support	OutSystems EI	OutSystems Auditability	OutSystems CIS
Article 5: Data minimisation	2	1	2	5	2	1	2	5
Article 6: Lawfulness (gating)	2	1	2	5	2	1	2	5
Article 7: Consent & withdrawal (delete account)	1	1	2	4	1	0	1	2
Article 25: Data protection by design/default	3	2	-	5	3	2	-	5
Article 32: Security of processing	3	2	3	8	3	2	3	8
Total CIS	27				25			

Table 4: Framework Matrix

7 ARTEFACT AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Artefact

The artefact produced through this study directly addresses the research problem: whether non-technical medical professionals can feasibly implement GDPR-relevant functionality in health applications using LCNC platforms. The artefact developed in this project is a practical decision-making framework designed to guide non-technical medical professionals in selecting appropriate LCNC platforms for developing health applications. The artefact consolidates this practical study into the comparative framework above and distilled recommendations, equipping future non-technical builders with an evidence-based guide for navigating compliance requirements in LCNC environments. These recommendations are not merely reflective but prescriptive, outlining technical requirements for each platform, and presenting practical pathways for leveraging LCNC tools within the unique constraints of clinical and healthcare innovation contexts.

7.1.1 Recommendations

7.1.1.1 Platform-Specific Recommendation

While regulatory compliance is a mandatory requirement for all health applications, the degree to which non-technical users can operationalise and sustain this compliance within LCNC platforms vary. Thus, beyond the baseline of GDPR and related data protection obligations, the primary differentiator lies in how effectively each platform supports non-technical medical professionals in embedding compliance into functional applications. This study shows that the most effective pathway for ensuring GDPR compliance in LCNC-based health applications is to adopt Mendix as the preferred platform where ease of implementation is a critical factor. Both Mendix and OutSystems provide the capacity to implement GDPR-compliant features to an extent. However, the evaluation demonstrated that Mendix offers an easier to implement environment for non-technical medical professionals. These affordances reduce the reliance on extensive developer input during early stages of development while still ensuring compliance with healthcare data protection standards. OutSystems, although powerful, demands greater technical intervention, especially when configuring complex logic. Consequently, for medical professionals without programming backgrounds if absolutely required, Mendix should be the preferred platform for initiating compliant application development.

Framework guidance: For non-technical medical professionals to take a more active role in digital tool creation, Mendix should be prioritised over OutSystems due to its stronger balance of ease of implementation and compliance readiness.

7.1.1.2 LCNC Primarily for Rapid Prototyping and Pilot Testing

LCNC platforms demonstrate their greatest value in contexts where rapid iteration is needed. For medical professionals without programming expertise, platforms such as Mendix and OutSystems allow immediate engagement with design processes through visual modelling and guided templates. Although they provide some compliance functionality for the development of health application, the evidence from this study indicates that features carrying evidentiary weight demanded additional configuration and verification and thus, they should primarily be positioned as tools for rapid prototyping and pilot testing in healthcare contexts, rather than as full enterprise-grade compliance solutions. While they significantly lower barriers to app creation for non-technical builders, the findings highlight persistent gaps in handling advanced GDPR requirements. By confining LCNC primarily to prototyping and pilot testing, there are benefits from fast, compliant experimentation without overextending the platform's limitations in governance. Once pilots are validated, the app can be transitioned into more technically mature environments, either within the LCNC ecosystem (with developer support) or into traditional development frameworks.

Framework guidance: Medical professionals should deploy LCNC primarily for rapid proof-of-concept development and pilot deployments, using these prototypes to validate regulatory compliance. Once validated, applications can either remain within the LCNC ecosystem or, if scaling or complex integrations are required, be transitioned into traditional development environments.

7.1.1.3 Adopt a Hybrid Development Model

While LCNC platforms considerably lower the technical barrier for application development, the findings of this study reinforce that they are not entirely sufficient for building robust, compliant health applications without some degree of technical oversight and thus, the most sustainable approach in this case is a hybrid model that combines LCNC development with technical professional oversight. Under this model, medical professionals contribute their domain knowledge and participate in the building phases, while experienced developers or IT specialists provide technical validation and ensure compliance with industry standards. This approach combines the accessibility and speed of LCNC platforms with the assurance of professional oversight, thereby mitigating risks and enhancing the quality of the final solution. In practical terms, this model creates a balance where innovation is not stifled by technical bottlenecks, yet patient safety, data security, and regulatory requirements remain uncompromised.

Framework guidance: LCNC use in healthcare should be framed not as a replacement for technical expertise but as a complement to it. Clinicians can build and express their requirements directly through LCNC platforms, but collaboration with IT and compliance teams remains necessary for

production deployment. A hybrid model mitigates risk while retaining the participatory benefits of LCNC platforms.

These three recommendations, taken together, highlight the practical pathways through which non-technical medical professionals can leverage LCNC platforms effectively in healthcare settings. They acknowledge both the strengths and limitations of the platforms, positioning them as enablers of innovation while ensuring that technical rigor and regulatory demands are not overlooked.

Platform	Ease of Implementation	Support Required	GDPR Readiness	Strengths	Limitations	Final Recommendation
Mendix	Designed for non-technical users with intuitive drag-and-drop UI and some level of simple logic.	Low to Moderate: basic compliance features achievable with minimal dev support	Supports GDPR features through built-in tools or templates, but some logic will prove difficult	Visual logic and workflows reduce tech complexity. Extensive documentation aimed at non-technical users.	Audit trails, consent withdrawal, and logging still require tedious manual setup. Limited granularity in some access controls. Marketplace modules may need tweaking which prove difficult for non-technical builders.	Best choice for medical professionals creating health apps. Use for prototyping, pilots, or combined with technical oversight.
Outsystems	Visually driven but requires	Moderate to High: complex	Full GDPR features are also	Powerful control over	Less intuitive for non-	Less suitable for non-

	more logic planning and system thinking.	features often need technical expertise or developer involvement	possible, but harder to configure without a technical background .	UI and backend Fine-grained field-level control More enterprise-ready if scaled	technical users Platform support leans toward developer audience Higher dev effort to configure consent/audit features	technical medical professionals. Majorly teams with developer support or technical oversight.
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Table 5: Platform recommendation matrix

7.2 Discussion

This study set out to evaluate whether low-code/no-code platforms can enable non-technical medical professionals to implement GDPR-relevant functionality in a chronic disease management application. The findings demonstrated that both Mendix and OutSystems provided sufficient baseline capability to deliver GDPR-aligned prototypes, though each exhibited distinct strengths and weaknesses across the evaluated articles. This section synthesises these results, highlighting implications for the feasibility of compliance-by-design in LCNC environments, trade-offs between ease of implementation and regulatory fidelity, and directions for future inquiry.

Overall Feasibility of GDPR Alignment in Low-Code Prototyping

The first and most important insight is that GDPR-aligned patterns: data minimisation, lawful-basis gating, consent management, privacy-by-design defaults, and processing security were achievable without enterprise licensing or custom back-end development. This indicates that LCNC platforms can substantially lower the barrier for health innovators, including medical professionals without programming experience, to create applications that at least point towards regulatory compliance. While implementation levels varied, the essential functional expectations of Articles 5, 6, 7, 25 and 32 were supported in both platforms at the level required for the study use-case.

Platform-Specific Strengths and Weaknesses

Despite this general feasibility, notable differences emerged. Mendix proved more approachable for data modelling and conceptual alignment of app structure with GDPR concepts such as lawful basis (Article 6) and consent (Article 7). OutSystems, by contrast, displayed an advantage in rapid form

construction and fine-grained field-level controls (Article 5), which reduced observed effort during data minimisation tasks. These advantages persisted when considering auditability and consent withdrawal. Mendix's reliance on marketplace modules or custom logic for audit trails imposed a light burden, while OutSystems could use light to moderate configuration to achieve comparable results. In contrast, while both platforms made consent capture straightforward, consent withdrawal through account deletion was more tractable in Mendix, albeit still requiring significant configuration.

In Articles 25 and 32, the platforms converged: secure defaults and role-based access were consistently achievable with minimal user intervention. Here, the platforms' architectures meant that regulatory expectations were largely met from the perspective of the builder, underscoring the extent to which compliance is platform-provided rather than builder-implemented. For this study, the granularity of role-based access control, specifically whether non-technical users can configure fine-grained, field-level access in addition to page-level controls, was not systematically evaluated. Only coarse role/page restrictions were exercised. As such, the findings do not establish how easily each platform supports more granular data protection configurations that may be relevant under Articles 5 and 32. The study also did not empirically examine resilience to misconfiguration, which is, the extent to which each platform enforces privacy-by-default settings, or blocks risky deployments. Because this was not tested, no claims are made regarding comparative safeguards or default enforcement strength.

Usability-Compliance Tensions

The results highlight a recurrent tension between the simplicity of low-code prototyping and the layered complexity of regulatory compliance. For example, minimizing data fields (Article 5) was trivial, yet logging changes to those fields in an auditable fashion demanded a conceptual leap into platform logic and entity relationships. Similarly, while consent capture could be implemented with a simple toggle, withdrawal required careful orchestration of deletion workflows to ensure cascade removal of personal data. These findings echo broader critiques of "compliance-by-design" paradigms, suggesting that low-code platforms reduce, but do not eliminate, the need for technical expertise when implementing features with evidentiary weight or irreversible data implications.

Implications for Health Technology Development

For non-technical innovators in digital health, the study provides cautious optimism. A clinician or researcher without formal training can, in principle, construct an app prototype that incorporates the fundamental safeguards demanded by GDPR. This has practical significance for early-stage projects and pilot deployments, where proof of concept must precede investment in full-scale engineering. However, the uneven effort required across articles, signals that compliance-critical applications

cannot be safely deployed without technical oversight. The platforms can guide regulatory awareness, but they stop short at guaranteeing end-to-end compliance.

Limitations of the Study

Several limitations temper the generalisability of these conclusions. First, the evaluation was restricted to two platforms; other LCNC environments, such as Microsoft Power Apps or Bubble, may handle GDPR requirements differently. Second, the test case centred on a single chronic-disease management prototype, which may not expose edge cases present in more complex clinical workflows. Third, although a “non-technical medical professional persona” was adopted, the results cannot fully simulate the experience of actual medical professionals with no platform familiarity. Finally, the CIS metric, while useful for standardised comparison, compresses nuanced implementation challenges into a simplified numerical scale.

Future Work

Future research could extend this work in several directions. First, user studies with genuine non-technical health professionals would provide more realistic insight into the accessibility of GDPR-compliant configuration. Second, expanding platform coverage would establish whether the observed patterns generalize across the broader LCNC ecosystem. Third, closer mapping of platform capabilities to the full spectrum of GDPR obligations, including rights of access, portability, and objection, would allow a more comprehensive assessment of compliance coverage. Finally, as platforms evolve, future studies could track whether platforms embed compliance regulations as discoverable defaults rather than optional modules or custom configurations.

8 CONCLUSION

This study has examined the capacity of low-code/no-code (LCNC) platforms to support GDPR compliance in the development of health applications by non-technical users. Rather than confirming a straightforward narrative of empowerment, the analysis reveals a more nuanced reality: LCNC platforms expand accessibility and reduce barriers to development, yet their compliance capabilities remain uneven and often dependent on some level of technical fluency.

Across the comparative assessment, a pattern emerges. Platforms offer increasingly user-friendly compliance features at the surface such as consent capture, logging modules, or basic encryption; but deeper, governance-critical elements like fine-grained access controls, auditable workflows, and proactive risk monitoring still require expert oversight. In effect, LCNC platforms democratise the form of compliance without fully transferring the function.

The contribution of this research lies in bringing a practice-based perspective into ongoing debates on LCNC in healthcare. Where scholarship often positions LCNC tools as inherently enabling, this study demonstrates that their value must be measured not only by availability of compliance functions but by the usability and enforceability of those functions in real-world workflows. By highlighting this distinction, the dissertation challenges overly optimistic assumptions and highlights the structural gap between platform design and regulatory obligation.

The key takeaway is that LCNC platforms lower the threshold for creating healthcare applications, but without governance embedded by default, non-technical developers risk reproducing compliance vulnerabilities rather than resolving them. Accessibility without assurance is not enough in domains where patient safety and data integrity are paramount.

Ultimately, if LCNC platforms are to fulfil their promise in regulated healthcare contexts, they must evolve from providing modular compliance add-ons to embedding governance-by-design as a foundational principle. Until such a shift occurs, their role will remain double-edged, opening opportunities for innovation, while simultaneously carrying hidden burdens of oversight that non-technical users may be ill-equipped to manage.

8.1 Appraisal of Objectives

Research Objective	Achievement
To identify the low-code/no-code (LCNC) platform used both in the industry and academia that offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing digital health applications for chronic disease management.	Conducted a structured selection process drawing on literature, industry usage reports, and academic references, which led to the identification of Mendix and OutSystems as suitable platforms for evaluation. These were chosen for their visibility in both professional and research contexts.

To define the core features of a typical chronic disease management application through research, and to use these features to design a benchmark prototype that will serve as a reference for evaluating low-code/no-code platforms.	A benchmark prototype was designed after reviewing existing literature on chronic disease management tools. Core features (patient registration, health monitoring, reminders, and secure data handling) were distilled and incorporated into a prototype used consistently across platforms for fair comparison.
To develop a chronic disease management app using each of the selected LCNC platforms.	The benchmark prototype was implemented separately in Mendix and OutSystems. While functional parity was maintained, each build exposed differences in platform compliance support, and ease of implementation.
To assess, compare, and evaluate each platform using appropriate metrics from the perspective of non-technical medical professionals.	Platforms were evaluated against compliance ability and suitability for healthcare contexts. Findings revealed accessibility strengths across platforms but also hidden reliance on technical fluency for deeper compliance.
To provide requirements for future LCNC development.	The study synthesised gaps into a set of design and compliance-oriented requirements for future LCNC platform evolution, including governance-by-default, simplified audit logging, and embedded compliance workflows. These requirements provide insights for potential users.

Table 6: Appraisal of objectives

8.2 Appraisal of Research Questions

This study set out to explore the capacity of low-code/no-code (LCNC) platforms to support non-technical medical professionals in developing GDPR-compliant digital health applications. The following reflects how each research question was addressed:

Research Question	Achievement
Which low-code/no-code (LCNC) platform offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing	This was answered through a comparative evaluation of Mendix and OutSystems using a benchmark prototype. Both platforms

digital health applications for chronic disease management?	demonstrated the capability to support GDPR-aligned development.
How do selected LCNC platforms compare in terms of compliance with GDPR requirements, and ease of development for non-technical medical professionals?	This question was addressed by evaluating both platforms against key GDPR Articles (5, 6, 7, 25, and 32), using the dual criteria of platform support and ease of implementation. Findings showed that while baseline compliance was feasible on both platforms without enterprise licensing, there were trade-offs in the level of configuration effort required.
How intuitive and accessible are the GDPR-related features for non-technical medical professionals on each LCNC platform?	This was partially addressed. Intuitiveness was assessed through constrained “non-technical personas,” highlighting where platform features were immediately usable versus where configuration became burdensome. However, the study did not incorporate the perspectives of actual medical professionals, and therefore accessibility is inferred rather than empirically validated.
What are the requirements of medical professionals when using low-code/no-code platforms to develop digital health applications?	This was addressed indirectly by deriving requirements from existing literature on digital health applications and regulatory expectations. These requirements, including data minimisation, lawful-basis gating, consent management, and privacy-by-design, were then operationalised in the app. Future work should complement this approach by eliciting requirements directly from medical professionals through interviews or surveys.

Table 7: Appraisal of research questions

8.3 Lessons Learned

Conducting this comparative analysis of low-code/no-code platforms has highlighted several important lessons. First, while all platforms promise ease of use for non-technical users, the degree of implementation and compliance features vary significantly, meaning platform choice must be aligned with the specific healthcare context rather than assumed to be universally suitable. Second,

hands-on implementation proved invaluable; evaluating features in practice offered insights that literature reviews alone could not capture.

The research also revealed challenges. The limited trial versions of the platforms restricted full exploration of advanced features, and comparing deployment processes within the project's timeline proved difficult. Additionally, aligning technical evaluation criteria with healthcare-specific needs such as GDPR compliance required careful balance.

Finally, the study underscored the importance of including end-user perspectives in future evaluations. While this project provided a technical and functional comparison, incorporating the experiences of medical professionals would offer a richer understanding in real-world settings.

Word Count: 6927 words.

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APPENDIX A: PROJECT PROPOSAL FORM

Project Proposal Form

Please refer to the **Project Handbook Section 4** when completing this form. Note that your proposal should be your own original work and you must cite sources in line with university guidance on **referencing and plagiarism**.

Degree Title:	Student's Name: Chukwuebuka Obiora
	Supervisor's Name: Dr Sofia Meacham
	Project Title/Area: Comparative Analysis of Low-Code/No-code Development Platforms for the Development of Health Applications by Non-Technical Medical Professionals.

Section 1: Project Overview

1.1 Problem definition - use one sentence to summarise the problem:

Despite the rapid growth of digital healthcare solutions in chronic disease management, widespread adoption remains limited due to the technical complexities of app development and the lack of technical expertise, particularly among medical professionals.

1.2 Project description - briefly explain your project:

This project aims to conduct a comparative analysis of selected low-code/no-code (LCNC) development platforms with a focus on compliance with data protection regulations (specifically the GDPR) and intuitive design for building digital health tools targeted at chronic disease management. Using a benchmark prototype with core features typical of chronic disease apps (reminders, monitoring logs), the study will implement the same design across multiple LCNC platforms. The outcomes will evaluate the usability of these platforms, with specific attention to the ease of implementing compliance and overall user experience for non-technical medical professionals in developing healthcare solutions.

1.3 Background - please provide brief background information, e.g., client, problem domain, and make reference to the literature (minimum 4-5 sources):

Chronic diseases, also known as noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), are health conditions that are of long duration and generally slow in progression (World Health Organization 2024). These conditions, including diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular conditions, continue to pose significant challenges to global

health systems. According to the World Health Organization (2024) NCDs are responsible for 41 million deaths annually, representing 75% of all deaths worldwide. Digital health interventions are being harnessed to enhance the management of chronic diseases (Pong et al. 2024). For example, Hamine et al. (2015) demonstrated that mobile health (mHealth) interventions such as short message service (SMS) reminders and mobile applications can improve treatment adherence and patient outcomes in chronic disease management. These technologies facilitated better self-management among patients.

Despite the promising outcomes of digital health tools, the development and implementation of these tools continue to face several challenges. Among these are the need for specialized technical expertise. Enabling medical professionals to develop digital health applications could significantly mitigate the challenges faced in harnessing digital health. Sanchis et al. (2019) in their work highlight the ability of LCNC platforms to enable development and deployment of applications by people with minimal coding knowledge.

Although digital health technologies offer advancements for improving chronic disease management, there is little research on the use of LCNC platforms to develop applications that provide core features typical of chronic disease apps. For this project, I will be employing the most prominent low-code/no-code platforms used in the industry and academia for the development process, and comparing them in terms of their suitability for medical professionals, particularly with regard to usability and their ability to support GDPR compliance under Articles 5, 6, 7, 25, and 32.

1.4 Research Questions

- Which low-code/no-code (LCNC) platform offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing digital health applications for chronic disease management?
- How do selected LCNC platforms compare in terms of usability, compliance with GDPR requirements, and ease of development for non-technical medical professionals?
- How intuitive and accessible are the GDPR-related features for non-technical medical professionals on each LCNC platform?
- What are the requirements of medical professionals when using low-code/no-code platforms to develop digital health applications?

1.5 Aims and objectives – what are the aims and objectives of your project? should be specific and measurable:

Aim: To evaluate and compare the effectiveness of selected low-code/no-code (LCNC) platforms in enabling non-technical medical professionals to develop chronic disease management applications

Objectives:

- To identify the low-code/no-code (LCNC) platform used both in the industry and academia that offers the most effective support for non-technical medical professionals in developing digital health applications for chronic disease management.

- To define the core features of a typical chronic disease management application through research, and to use these features to design a benchmark prototype that will serve as a reference for evaluating low-code/no-code platforms.
- To develop a chronic disease management app using each of the selected LCNC platforms.
- To assess, compare, and evaluate each platform using appropriate metrics from the perspective of non-technical medical professionals.
- To provide requirements for future LCNC development.

Section 2: Artefact

2.1 What is the artefact that you intend to produce?

The artefact for this project will be a framework designed to guide non-technical medical professionals in selecting appropriate LCNC platforms for developing health applications. The artefact will provide a comprehensive analysis of the platforms. It will include an evaluation of the applications in terms of ease of implementation, compliance with GDPR requirements, and suitability for chronic disease management contexts. Furthermore, it will present clear recommendations and platform-specific requirements for future development by non-technical medical professionals. Together, these artefacts will offer both a tangible demonstration of LCNC capabilities and a detailed framework for guiding future digital health application development using such platforms.

2.2 How is your artefact actionable (i.e., routes to implementation and exploitation in the technology domain)?

This artefact will be actionable by demonstrating real-world feasibility of LCNC platforms, allowing medical professionals to assess how digital tools can be developed without deep technical expertise. The artefact will provide an evaluation framework. By defining key development requirements and evaluating limitations, this artefact will show how LCNC solutions can reduce reliance on technical teams, speed up digital tool creation, and improve healthcare access while also maintaining relevant GDPR standards.

Section 3: Evaluation

3.1 How are you going to evaluate your project artefact?

The project artefact will be evaluated through a structured framework that assesses each platform against GDPR compliance touchpoints. Specifically, the evaluation will focus on three themes:

- **Ease of Implementation (EI):** The level of effort required for non-technical builders to configure GDPR-aligned features.
- **Support:** The extent to which platform defaults, documentation, and built-in features assist compliance without additional configuration.

- **Auditability:** The degree to which the platforms generate usable records of key security and privacy events that can serve as evidence of compliance.

Each platform will be rated across these themes using a Compliance Implementation Score (CIS), which aggregates findings into a comparative metric. This ensures that the evaluation is not purely technical but aligned with the project's aim of identifying the most suitable LCNC platform for non-technical healthcare builders working under GDPR constraints.

3.2 How does this project relate to your MSc Programme and your degree title outcomes?

This project aligns directly with the core themes of my MSc Digital Health programme, particularly in areas such as healthcare technology innovation, digital system development, and user-centred solution design. It integrates key areas of my programme, like human-centred design, health information systems, smart systems, and research methods for health and social care. This project contributes to my programme's objectives by demonstrating my ability to develop, and evaluate digital health solutions that enhance patient outcomes, and support clinical decision-making. Overall, the project serves as a capstone to my programme's goal of leveraging digital technologies to improve health service delivery and patient outcomes.

3.3 What are the risks in this project and how are you going to manage them?

Identified Risk	Mitigation
Time management issues – Risk of project delays due to workload	Follow the plan outlined in the structured Gantt chart with weekly progress reviews.
Technical Challenges (Loss of data)	Progress will be constantly backed up to the cloud to prevent loss of work.
Difficulty finding professionals for evaluation in time.	Reach out early enough to potential experts for the evaluation phase.

Section 4: References

4.1 Please provide references if you have used any.

Reference list

Bente, B. E., Anne Van Dongen, Ruud Verdaasdonk and Lisette van Gemert-Pijnen, 2024. eHealth implementation in Europe: a scoping review on legal, ethical, financial, and technological aspects. *Frontiers in digital health*, 6.

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World Health Organization, 2024. *Noncommunicable Diseases* [online]. World Health Organization. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>.

Section 5: Academic Practice and Ethics

Please delete as appropriate.

5.1 Have you made yourself familiar with, and understand, the University guidance on Yes
referencing and plagiarism?

5.2 Do you acknowledge that this project proposal is your own work and that it does Yes
not contravene any academic offence as specified in the University's regulations?

Section 6: Proposed Plan (please attach your Gantt chart below)

APPENDIX B: ETHICS APPROVAL

Research Ethics Checklist

About Your Checklist	
Ethics ID	65316
Date Created	24/04/2025 16:30:46
Status	Approved
Date Approved	13/05/2025 14:54:49
Risk	Low

Researcher Details	
Name	Obiora Obiora
Faculty	Faculty of Science & Technology
Status	Postgraduate Taught (Masters, MA, MSc, MBA, LLM)
Course	MSc Digital Health

Project Details	
Title	The Development of a Mobile Application for Personalized Diabetes Management Using a No-code/Low-code Multi-Agent Platform.
Start Date of Project	19/05/2025
End Date of Project	05/09/2025
Proposed Start Date of Data Collection	19/06/2025
Supervisor	Sofia Meacham
Approver	Sofia Meacham

Summary - no more than 600 words (including detail on background methodology, sample, outcomes, etc.)

The project focuses on developing a personalized diabetes management application for diabetes patients through the use of no-code/low-code platforms. Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels due to the body's inability to produce or effectively use insulin. Despite the availability of digital health tools for management of diabetes, there is barely any platform that incorporates intelligent agents to enhance monitoring, diet optimization, medication adherence, and emergency intervention. The proposed application aims to address this gap by incorporating intelligent agents to handle the various important aspects when it comes to the management of diabetes.

Filter Question: Is your study solely literature based?

Additional Details	
Will you have access to personal data that allows you to identify individuals which is not already in the public domain?	No
Will you have access to confidential corporate or company data (that is not covered by confidentiality terms)	No

within an agreement or separate confidentiality agreement)?	
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Storage, Access and Disposal of Research Data

Where will your research data be stored and who will have access during and after the study has finished.

All research data will be kept on a password-protected and encrypted server, ensuring that only authorized personnel can access it. The only authorized personnel will be me.

Once your project completes, will your dataset be added to an appropriate research data repository such as BORDaR, BU's Data Repository?	No
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Please explain why you do not intend to deposit your research data on BORDaR? E.g. do you intend to deposit your research data in another data repository (discipline or funder specific)? If so, please provide details.

NOT APPLICABLE

APPENDIX C: PROJECT FIRST PROGRESS REVIEW

9/3/25, 3:57 AM

Feedback for First Progress Review (FEEDBACK ONLY) - Individual Masters Project (May) 24/25 - Brightspace | BU

Masters Project First Progress Review

Activity: First Progress Review (FEEDBACK ONLY)

Course: Individual Masters Project (May) 24/25

Name: Obiora Obiora

Criteria	Yes	To some extent	No
Definition of the problem - Has the problem been defined, has the artefact been identified and have objectives been set?	✓		
Review of literature and related work - Is there evidence of appropriate research?	✓		
Methodology and Artefact - Is there evidence of appropriate analysis of the problem and design of a solution and appropriate evaluation?		✓	
Dissertation - Have sections of the dissertation been written and has the Supervisor seen these?	✓		

Overall Score

Satisfactory	Requires minor improvement	Requires major improvement (at some risk of failing the project)	Unsatisfactory (at high risk of failing the project)	Invalid - Proposal not approved	Invalid - Proposal not submitted	Invalid - Ethics checklist not approved	Invalid Ethics checklist not submitted
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APPENDIX D: PROJECT SCREENS

Onboarding Screen

Onboarding Screen

Onboarding Screen

Home Screen

Explore Screen

Monitor Screen

Appointment Reminder Screen

Appointment Reminder Screen 2

Medication Addition Screen

APPENDIX E: ITEMS IN THE LARGE FILE SUBMISSION

Items in the Large File:

- Project Findings
- Project Artefact
- App Screens